

Effect of Hands-on Activities on Students' Academic Performance in Plane Shapes in Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

OLADAYO, Chizoba Eugenia¹ & DIRI, Erepanmowei Ayibakuro²

^{1&2}Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education,

Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

oladayoce@fuotuoke.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826328>

Abstract

This study investigated the effect of hands-on activities on the academic performance of students in geometry. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, aiming to establish a cause-and-effect relationship through the experimental design. The population consisted of 1,346 Upper Basic II (JSS 2) students in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. One intact class from each school made up the sample of 83 students from two co-educational schools. 45 students constituted the experimental group, while 38 students formed the control group. Activity Oriented Mathematics Test Items (AOMTI) was used as the major instrument for this study. This activity focused on plane shapes (2D Shapes in Geometry, Mathematics) and 3D shapes (Cylinder, cube, cuboid, cone). The test was validated for face and content by two specialists in mathematics and measurement and evaluation. The reliability coefficient, established through the test-retest procedure using the Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), yielded a coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation were employed to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to test the null hypotheses at a significance level of .05. The research outcomes indicated a significant disparity between students taught plane shapes with hands-on activities in their posttest, suggesting that hands-on activities served as a more effective learning approach. Finally, gender was found to be a factor in the Hands-on activity, in favour of the male students. Consequently, the researcher recommended the provision of standard mathematics laboratories and adequate instructional materials to facilitate students' engagement in necessary activities.

Keywords: Hands-on Activities, Geometry, academic performance, Students.

Introduction

Mathematics education, as emphasized by Mayowa (2011), holds the key to achieving social and economic development by instilling essential human values in children. It encompasses both classroom instruction and learning experiences beyond its confines. A primary aim of secondary school mathematics is to nurture creative and constructive thinking in individuals. Since its inception, mathematics has played a pivotal role in shaping the culture and intellectual landscape of societies worldwide, as noted by Emeniru (2019). Eya (2017) contends that mathematics is integral to human culture, and the education system is instrumental in its transmission. Teaching mathematics is an effective means of fostering critical thinking skills in young learners. The extent

and caliber of mathematical education provided within a nation's school system profoundly influence its prosperity. According to Ezeom and Afe (2007), mathematics serves as a cultural tool enabling individuals to comprehend and interact with their environment, both immediate and distant. Through systematic and logical reasoning, mathematics offers solutions to human challenges across various domains of life, illuminating the boundless potential of the human intellect (Onifade, 2017).

Mathematics holds a pivotal role in education, serving as a catalyst for social, economic, and technological progress in every society. Its comprehension relies on effective teaching and instruction within educational institutions. The significance of mathematics extends beyond individual learning to impact society as a whole, and nations aspiring for global recognition must prioritize investments in science and technology. According to Achimugu (2014), hands-on science learning allows students to validate scientific theories, laws, and principles, thereby enhancing their capacity and interest in mastering mathematics. Moreover, regular engagement with mathematical concepts sharpens the mind's ability to analyze and solve complex problems, fostering improved performance in mathematics. For instance, the teachers of mathematics utilizing activity based materials and allowing students to manipulate these materials more frequently in their teaching will enhance students learning, retention and mastery of any concept taught.

The teaching and learning of mathematics have emerged as significant concerns among educators, as highlighted by Garba (2013). Kolawole and Udeh (2012) underscore the direct correlation between a nation's advancement in science, technology, and industry and the proficiency of its citizens in mathematics. Despite its relevance, Mefor (2014) bemoans the lackluster performance of students in mathematics, noting a prevalent disdain for the subject and subsequent poor academic outcomes in recent years. Numerous research endeavors have sought to identify the challenges associated with mathematics education and propose solutions for improved achievement (Olawejaju, 2014). Factors hindering students' success in mathematics encompass various aspects, including background issues, lack of interest or negative attitudes toward the subject, as well as teacher-related factors such as inadequate preparation, shortage of qualified instructors, insufficient instructional materials, and ineffective teaching methodologies (Usman, 2011; Olorunyomi, 2013; Haruna, 2014). Jegede (2014) further highlights subpar performance in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE), particularly concerning candidates aspiring for science-based courses or those needing mathematics as a prerequisite for higher education admission in Nigeria.

However, students' performance in mathematics is sometimes affected negatively by some ethical issues such as, the relationship between the students and the teacher. Sometimes, exploitation, discrimination, and favoritism, play down on students' performance in mathematics. Other issues such as the contents of the curriculum, availability of resources, assessment pattern, bias in culture, etc affect the performance and engagement of students in mathematics. Teachers and those concerned should pay attention to these and address them.

Effective methods for supporting students' performance in mathematics extend beyond traditional approaches. Research suggests that incorporating alternative methods such as collaborative

groups, manipulatives and hands-on activities can yield significant benefits (Curtain-Phillips, 2000; Wolodko, Willson, & Johnson, 2003). Manipulatives are the use of physical objects or materials to represent abstract concepts. While hands-on activities involves direct participation and engagement in a task. It can include experiments, stimulations, crafts and projects. Thus, Manipulatives differs from hands-on activities. By engaging in these varied approaches, students not only gain confidence in their mathematical abilities but also enhance their higher-order thinking skills and establish connections to real-world applications. Furthermore, utilizing alternative methods fosters an environment where students develop the ability to question the meanings and purposes of mathematics. Through hands-on activities and other experiential learning opportunities, teachers prioritize the acquisition of mathematics skills within a context that encourages exploration and critical thinking.

Hands-on activities encompass a method of instruction wherein learners acquire knowledge through direct experience. This approach involves students, spanning primary, secondary, and tertiary levels, actively engaging with and manipulating the objects pertinent to their learning. By immersing themselves in hands-on activities, students transition from passive recipients to active participants in the teaching and learning process within the classroom. Haury and Rillero (1994) characterize hands-on activities as offering students a comprehensive learning experience tailored to individual abilities, fostering critical thinking skills. In this experiential learning paradigm, students are not merely passive recipients of information delivered through lectures; instead, they actively interact with the subject matter to solve problems. Often referred to as experiential or experimental learning, this hands-on approach empowers students to immerse themselves in the subject matter, thereby enhancing understanding and bolstering self-confidence.

Abudullai (2013) defines hands-on activities as a teaching method that actively involves students in classroom activities, utilizing both their hands and intellect under the guidance of the teacher. This approach enables learners to demonstrate proficiency in materials and practical tasks, utilizing their hands or other mechanical skills. Hands-on activities inherently provide students with tangible objects for direct investigation. The classroom setting offers a plethora of benefits for both learners and educators. When students are encouraged to apply classroom concepts in real-world scenarios, it fosters a learner-centric environment that enhances comprehension and promotes personal and social development. Moreover, learners engaged in activity-based learning within the classroom exhibit higher levels of motivation, enhanced retention of learned material, and improved academic performance (Ryan & Deci, 2017).

Hussain & Akhtar (2013) assert that hands-on activities can foster creativity and higher-order learning. This approach is inclusive and adaptable to various types of learners. Rather than being considered solely as a learning style, hands-on learning should be an integral component of every lesson plan, providing students with familiarity, with models and materials they will encounter in secondary school, professional, and advanced educational settings. The usefulness of Hands-on activities cannot be over emphasized. It adds to the motivation of students and involvement in the learning process. (Lappan, et al., 2006). Learning of abstract mathematical concepts are enhanced by Hands-on activities strategy (Moyer, 2001). Problem-solving skills and abilities are developed and improved by this strategy (Shaughnessy & Gitelman, 2005). It leads to skill acquisition and

development thereby facilitating critical reasoning (Battista, 2007). This learner-centered approach allows students to interact with, touch, and manipulate objects during the learning process.

Academic achievement, as Downes (2015) defines it, encompasses the extent to which students, teachers, or institutions attain their short or long-term educational goals, including cumulative grade point averages (GPAs) and completion of educational degrees such as high school and bachelor's degrees. Achor, Imoko, and Ajai (2010) characterize academic achievement as the acquisition of knowledge, which can be measured through examinations or continuous assessments. Numerous factors influence students' academic achievement, including family background, individual differences, cognitive factors, motivation, self-control, extracurricular activities, and attitudes. Hands-on activities have a positive effect on the achievement of secondary school students' in geometry (Moyer, 2001; Shaughnessy & Gitelman, 2005). The activities help learners to view, understand and utilise concepts in geometric. This assists students to have a better knowledge, as well as internalizing and remembering taught concepts.

Moreover, two dimensional and three dimensional shapes are very useful in human daily life in the sense that they are applicable in architecture, such as building construction, such as 3D drawing to draw the building plan, block molding, ceiling, flooring, roofing, bridge building, etc. (Ching, 2014). These shapes are utilized in every aspect of human endeavour, they give shape names to every object one can think of. For functionality and efficiency, 2D and 3D shapes are utilized by electronics and machine devices as posited by (Gottfried, 2016). They are also utilized in navigation and transportation, computer graphics, development of games, furniture and product design, Arts and design, Science and Medicine, etc. (Lynch, 2017; Hoyt, 2017; Nickel, 2013; Kerlow 2009).

Gender, as described by Obih (2020), refers to socially constructed roles assigned to individuals based on societal and cultural norms. Distinctions between males and females in terms of mental, emotional, and behavioral attributes, as well as societal roles and expectations, stem from gender constructs. Gender issues are particularly pertinent in mathematics education, given the emphasis on bolstering technological manpower and increasing female representation in science and technology fields. Yara (2010) emphasizes that one's potential is not determined by gender and asserts that both males and females are equal in all respects, especially intellectually. Various teaching methods can be employed to promote gender-fair teaching in the classroom, thereby addressing gender-related concerns and ensuring equal opportunities for all students. Ultimately, it is the responsibility of educators to explore teaching methods that accommodate gender diversity in the classroom.

However, despite the critical role of mathematics in advancing science and technology, students continue to exhibit poor performance in external examinations. Several factors contribute to this issue, including students' struggle to connect theoretical knowledge with real-world applications, the use of ineffective teaching methods in mathematics instruction, students' perception of many secondary curriculum topics as challenging, inadequate instructional materials, absence of mathematics laboratories, and limited exposure to common mathematical equipment and

methodologies. In light of these challenges, the researcher undertook this study to investigate the impact of hands-on activities on students' academic performance in geometry.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of Hands-on activities on students' academic performance in geometry in Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the effects of Hands-on activities on students' academic performance in plane shapes.
2. Investigate the influence of Hands-on activities on students' academic performance in plane shapes geometry with respect to gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean difference between the scores of the students taught plane shapes using Hands-on activities and those taught using traditional teaching methods?
2. What is the mean difference between the scores of male and female students taught plane shapes using Hands-on activities method?

Hypotheses

H₀₁. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught plane shapes using Hands-on activities and those taught with the use of traditional teaching method.

H₀₂. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students taught plane shapes with the use of Hands-on activities.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental non-randomized pre-test, post-test control group design to establish a cause-and-effect relationship. Intact classes were randomly allocated to the experimental and control groups. The population of the study comprises 1,346 Upper Basic II (JSS II) students in the 41 secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. Two co-educational schools were randomly selected for the study tagged Schools I and II. One intact class from both schools made up the sample of 83 students. 45 students from School I formed the experimental group (28 males and 17 females), while 38 students from School II formed the control group. The experimental group were practically drilled on hands-on activities. They were taught using a lesson plan filled with different students' activities. They were provided with items which include: cardboard papers of different colours cut into units of plane shapes, scissors, razor blades, measurement rule, glue and sellotapes, among others, the cardboard papers were pre-cut and also left for students to cut and form various plane shapes with guidance of the researchers. While the control groups were taught using conventional lecture method with the lesson note prepared for the group. These were the treatments given to the two groups.

Activity Oriented Mathematics Test Items (AOMTI) was used as the major instrument for this study. A pre-test items prepared using table of specification which covered the topics, plane shapes (2D shapes), and (3D) shapes such as cylinder, cube, cuboid, cone, etc. which had been treated in the class for 4 weeks was administered to the two groups before the prepared programmed teaching using the Hands-on-Activities Approach, and their scores were collected. Their teachers were also instructed on how to use the prepared lesson notes on the topic selected for the activities. The teaching lasted for four weeks and after which the same pre-test questions were reshuffled and administered to the two groups as posttest to observe their involvement, performance and method of solving those problems. The mathematics teachers were there to ensure that the learners adhered to the instructions provided. By the end of one hour, the papers were collected from the students by the researchers and assessed using the prepared marking scheme. Their scores were also collected. In the test items, ten activity-oriented questions were drawn from the topic. The setting of the questions was carefully done to avoid ambiguity. Research assistants marked the post-test using the marking scheme developed by the researchers. Face and content validity were established by specialists in mathematics, measurement and evaluation. The instrument's reliability coefficient was determined through trial testing with a randomly selected group of 25 Upper Basic II students. Test-retest procedure yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation were utilized to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. ANCOVA was utilised since, the research employed the use of intact classes and the instrument of Pretest and Posttest for the study.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the mean difference between the achievement scores of students taught plane shapes with Hands-on activities and those taught using traditional teaching methods?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviations of students taught plane shapes with Hands-on activities and those taught using traditional method.

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Hands-on	45	65.80	6.79	84.91	5.92	19.11
Lecture	38	63.08	5.81	74.74	6.33	11.66

The result in table 1 shows that the mean score of the pretest of those in the experimental group taught plane shapes using Hand on activity method is 65.80, while their post-test is 84.91. The mean gain is 19.11. Also, the mean score of the pretest and posttest of those in control group

taught plane shapes using conventional method are 63.08 and 74.74 respectively. The mean gain is 11.66. The gain in mean of 19.11 for the experimental group is greater than the 11.66 gain in mean for the control group.

Research Question 2: What is the mean difference between the scores of male and female students taught plane shapes using Hands-on activities method in their pretest and posttest?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught plane shapes with Hands-on activities in their pretest and posttest.

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	28	67.61	5.74	87.96	4.01	20.35
Female	17	62.82	7.49	79.88	5.10	17.06

The result in table 2 shows that the mean scores of the pretest and posttest of males in the experimental group taught plane shapes using Hand on activity are 67.61 ± 5.74 and 87.96 ± 4.01 , their mean gain is 20.35. While the mean scores of the pretest and posttest of their female counterparts are 62.82 ± 7.49 and 79.88 ± 5.10 . The mean gain is 17.06. The gain in mean of 20.35 for males is greater than that of the females which is 17.06, in favour of male students.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught plane shapes with Hands-on activities and those taught with the traditional method.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance of academic performance of students taught plane shapes with Hands-on activities and traditional methods

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected Model	2137.211 ^a	2	1068.605	28.322	.000
Intercept	4690.408	1	4690.408	124.312	.000
Pretest	4.537	1	4.537	.120	.730
Group	1997.557	1	1997.557	52.942	.000
Error	3018.476	80	37.731		
Total	539721.000	83			
Corrected Total	5155.687	82			

a. R Squared = .415 (Adjusted R Squared = .400)

The result in table 3 indicated that there is a significant difference, $F(1, 80) = 52.94, p = .00 < .05$, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies a significant difference between the academic performance of students taught geometry using hands-on activities and the traditional method as reflected in the mean and standard deviation. Thus, the hands-on activities is more effective.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught plane shapes with Hands-on activities.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance on mean achievement scores of male and female students taught plane shapes using Hands-on activities.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected Model	693.713 ^a	2	346.856	17.181	.000

Intercept	3116.758	1	3116.758	154.380	.000
Pretest	2.797	1	2.797	.139	.712
Gender	637.402	1	637.402	31.572	.000
Error	847.932	42	20.189		
Total	325987.000	45			
Corrected Total	1541.644	44			

a. R Squared = .450 (Adjusted R Squared = .424)

The result in table 4 indicated that there is a significant difference, $F(1, 42) = 31.57, p = .00 < .05$, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies a significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught geometry using hands-on activities and the traditional method as reflected in the mean and standard deviation.

Discussion

The study's findings indicate that students taught plane shapes using hands-on activities outperformed those taught through traditional methods, suggesting that hands-on activities are a more effective learning approach. This aligns with the results of Hoke (2008), whose research demonstrated improved student performance on measurement tasks when hands-on activities were utilized. Additionally, the findings are consistent with studies by Oludipe, Ojediran, and Kareem (2020); Kehinde, Saddiq, and Sabitu (2022); Daramola, Oyerinde, and Fabiyi (2022); and Oluwatosin (2013), all of which observed significant differences in academic performance favoring students taught with hands-on activities.

Furthermore, the study revealed that male students taught plane shapes using hands-on activities achieved higher scores than their female counterparts, indicating a significant gender difference favoring males. This finding corroborates the results of Daramola, Oyerinde, and Fabiyi (2022), which noted a significant interaction effect between gender and hands-on teaching method. However, it contradicts the findings of Oluwatosin (2013), which found no significant difference in achievement scores between male and female students taught stoichiometry using hands-on activities. Similarly, Kehinde, Saddiq, and Sabitu (2022) reported no significant difference in achievement between male and female pupils taught fractions using hands-on activities.

Conclusion

The study examined the impact of hands-on activities on students' academic performance in plane shapes. Analysis of the results indicated that students instructed through hands-on activities achieved higher academic performance compared to those taught using traditional methods. Additionally, there was a notable difference in academic performance based on gender. The findings underscore the effectiveness of hands-on activities in improving students' mathematical performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Ensure the availability of standard mathematics laboratories and an adequate supply of instructional materials to facilitate hands-on activities for students.

2. Encourage mathematics teachers to embrace the use of hands-on activities as an effective teaching method for geometry instruction.
3. Advocate for flexibility in teaching methods among mathematics educators, emphasizing the incorporation of various approaches, particularly hands-on activities, to enhance student performance.
4. Raise awareness among mathematics teachers about the potential benefits of hands-on activities in teaching, encouraging their utilization to improve students' mathematical performance.
5. Implement training programs for mathematics teachers to familiarize them with the application of hands-on activities in teaching geometry and other mathematical topics.
6. Organize seminars, conferences, and workshops by the Ministry of Education and school administrators to highlight the importance of hands-on activities in teaching geometry and other mathematical concepts, fostering professional development among educators.

References

- Abudullai, A. A. (2013). Teachers' involvement in the use of hand-on laboratory methods in teaching. *International Journal of Education*, 3(11), 234-237.
- Achimugu, L. (2014). *Teaching basic science for creativity*. The use of cooperative group assignment, STAN proceeding.
- Achor, K., Imoko, K., & Ajai, B. (2010). Influence of gender and ability on senior secondary school students achievement on the concept of culture and the society. *International Journal of Education*. 34, 234-256.
- Battista, M. T. (2007). *The development of geometric and spatial thinking*. In F. K. Lester Jr. (Ed.), *Second handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning* (pp. 843-908). Information Age Publishing.
- Ching, F. D. K. (2014). *Architecture: Form, space, and order* John Wiley & Sons.
- Curtain-Phillips, M. (2000). *The causes and prevention of math anxiety*. Retrieved March 5, 2024, from http://www.mathgoodies.com/articles/math_anxiety.html
- Daramola, K. R., Oyerinde, O. O., Fabiyi, T. R. (2022). Effects of hand-on teaching method on senior secondary mathematics students' performance in Ondo State. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 4(2). www.irjmets.com
- Downes, M. (2015). Applying the subject "Cell" through constructivist approach during science lessons and the teacher's view. *Journal of Environmental Science*, 2(1), 3-13.
- Emeniru (2019). Science, Technology and Mathematics Education as a tool for meeting the millennium development goals in Nigeria. *Oju Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education*. 1(2), 1-5.
- Eya, H. C. (2017). Unpacking pedagogical content knowledge: Conceptualizing and measuring teachers' topic-specific Knowledge of Students. *Journal of Research in Mathematics Education*, 39 (4), 372- 400.
- Ezeom, A. E., & Afe, J. J. (2007). Effect of concept mapping method of instruction on students' achievement and retention in mathematics. *Nigerian Journal of Functional Education*, 5(1), 12-15.
- Garba, A. (2013). *Effect of activity-based method on students' achievement and interest in*

- Integrated Science among junior secondary students in Akwanga local Government Area of Nasarawa State* [Unpublished masters' dissertation], Nasarawa State University, Keffi.
- Gottfried, B. S. (2016). *Engineering, Design and Problem Solving*. Springer.
- Haruna, A. (2014). *Effect of demonstration approach on senior secondary students' achievement and retention in Chemistry*. [Unpublished masters' dissertation], Nasarawa State University, Keffi.
- Haurry, D. L. & Rillero, P. (1994). *Perspectives of hands-on science teaching*. Retrieved March 2, 2023 from <http://www.ncrel.org/sdrs/areas/issues/content/cntareas/science/eric/eric-toc.htm>.
- Hoke, D. (2008). *Effects on student performance of using hands-on activities to teach seventh grade students' measurement concepts*. [Electronic Theses and Dissertations]. <https://stars.library.ucf.edu/etd/3667>
- Hoyt, J. (2017). *Product Design for Engineers*. CRC Press.
- Hussain, M., & Akhtar, M. (2013). Impact of hands-on activities on students' achievement in science: An experimental evidence from Pakistan. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 16. 626-632.
- Jegede, F. A. (2014). The knowledge base for learning in Science and Technology Education. *African Science and Technology Education in the new millennium; practice, policy and priorities*. 151-176. Kenny 1: Jutalsco Limited.
- Kehinde, M. A., Saddiq, K., & Sabitu, K. A. (2022). The effect of hands-on activities on primary school pupils' achievement and retention in fraction. *Abacus (Mathematics Education Series)* 46(1), 88-98.
- Kerlow, I. V. (2009). *The art of 3D computer animation and effects*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kolawole E. B., & Udeh D. O. (2012). Head circumference as a predictor of aptitude performance in mathematics. *Crown research in education*, 2(2), 245–264.
- Lappan, G., Phillips, E., & Winter, M. (2006). The impact of hands-on activities on student learning in geometry. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 25(2), 157-171.
- Lynch, K. (2017). *The image of the city* MIT Press.
- Mayowa, A. A. (2011). *Effect of constructivist-based instructional model on students' conceptual change and retention in Biology*. [Unpublished Ph.D. thesis]. Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.
- Mefor, C. (2014). *Nigeria: Identifying Problems of Poor Performance in Mathematics and Way Out*. Retrieved on March 9, 2024 from <http://allafrica.com/stories/201101200591.html>
- Moyer, P. S. (2001). Are we having fun yet? How teachers use manipulatives to teach mathematics. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 47(2), 175-197.
- Nickel, G. (2013). *Mathematics in everyday life*. Greenwood.
- Obih, S. A. O. (2020). *Relative effectiveness of cooperative, discovery and inquiry methods on secondary school students' achievement in economics in Imo State*. [Unpublished doctoral thesis]. Abia State University, Uturu, Abia State.
- Olarewaju, A. O. (2014). *New approaches to the teaching of integrated science*. Ibadan: Alafas Publishing Company. Heineman Educational Books (Nigeria) Plc.
- Olorunyomi, A. A. (2013). *Effect of experiential teaching method on students' achievement in Chemistry* [Unpublished Masters' dissertation], Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.
- Oludipe, D. I., Ojediran, I. A., & Kareem, A. O. (2020). Effect of hands-on/minds-on activities on junior secondary school basic science students' learning outcomes in Ogun State, Nigeria.

- FUDMA Journal of Educational Foundations (FUJEF)*, 3(1), 52-67. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346398357>
- Oluwatosin, V. A. (2013). *Effect of hands-on activities on senior secondary chemistry students' achievement and retention in stoichiometry in zone c of Benue State* [Published masters' dissertation], Benue State University, Makurdi. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=299280>
- Onifade, A. P. (2017). Developing pre-service teachers understanding of fractions through Problem Posing. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(1), 166-175.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Shaughnessy, J. M. & Gitelman, A. (2005). Teaching Geometry to students with learning difficulties. *Mathematics Teacher*, 98(6), 434-438.
- Tile, M. T. (2013). *Effect of activity-based on psychomotor skills acquisition and interest of senior secondary 2 in Biology* [Unpublished masters' dissertation], Benue State University, Makurdi.
- Usman, K. O. (2011). Using guided scoring teaching strategy to improve students' achievement in mathematics at secondary school level in Nigeria. *Journal of the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*, 42(1&2), 60-65.
- Wolodko, B., Willson, K., & Johnson, R. (2003). Metaphors as a vehicle for exploring preservice teachers' perceptions of mathematics. *Teaching Children Mathematics*, 10(4), 224-229.
- Yara, P. O. (2010). Adequacy of resources materials and achievement of senior secondary schools